

Quinolino-bromopyrones and their Conversion into Quinolino-furans.

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The bromination of quinolino-pyrones, dissolved in carbon tetrachloride or in glacial acetic acid, which was carried out with the intention of obtaining quinolino-bromopyrones, was found to proceed in a complex manner. On resorting to the bromo-nitro- and the bromo-amino-coumarins (Dey and Row, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 113, 379) the authors found that quinolino-bromopyrones could be obtained from these through the Skraup and the Doebner-Miller synthesis. For instance :—

The quinolino-bromopyrones are colourless substances insoluble in water, dissolving very sparingly in alcohol, and more readily in boiling chloroform or in carbon tetrachloride which are the best media for crystallisation. The salts with hydrochloric, with nitric, and with sulphuric acid separate as crystals when a solution of the

base in the concentrated acid is diluted with about its own volume of water. The methiodides are partially resolved into their constituents on evaporating their aqueous solutions on the water-bath. The hydrogenations of the pyridine ring in these substances proceeds smoothly enough, the resulting tetrahydro-quinolino-bromopyrones resembling the reduction products of the unsubstituted quinolinopyrones in all respects, *e.g.*, colour, crystalline form and solubility.

Cold dilute caustic soda has no appreciable action on these substances but on warming they gradually dissolve to an almost colourless solution from which acids of the coumaridic type are precipitated on acidification. The change, which is effected most readily by boiling alcoholic potash, is represented as follows :—

The quinolinofuran carboxylic acids obtained in this way crystallise from boiling water in soft, colourless needles which are stable and neither melt nor decompose at temperatures below 300°. They have an amphoteric character, dissolving both in acids and alkalis in the cold and are esterified with ease on saturating the alcoholic solution with hydrogen chloride, the ester hydrochlorides being deposited under these conditions. When warmed with sulphuric acid they display the change of colours characteristic of substances that have the benzo-furan structure. On heating with soda lime to dull redness, the acids split off carbon dioxide and yield the quinolino-furans, a class of heterocyclic substances that appears not to have been described before. These quinolino-furans

are pronounced bases, and readily dissolve in dilute acids from which ammonia precipitates them as white emulsions which slowly solidify on standing forming hard cubical crystals. They are stable and remain unaffected by hot alkali.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Quinolino-6:5- α -3-bromopyrone.

3-Bromo-6-nitro-coumarin (8 gms.) was intimately mixed with dry glycerol (10 c.c.), and sulphuric acid (8 c.c.) was slowly added with stirring. The mixture was heated gradually in an oil-bath; at about 140° a vigorous reaction took place and the mass began to swell. The flask was taken out of the oil-bath, shaken well and cooled, and when the vigour of the reaction had subsided, the temperature was slowly raised to 170° and kept between 170 - 180° for 6 hours. The dark mass was then cooled and extracted with boiling water repeatedly till the filtrate ceased to show any colour. The solution was rendered alkaline with sodium carbonate when a yellowish green flocculent precipitate of impure quinolino-bromopyrone separated.

It is insoluble in ether and in benzene and very sparingly soluble in cold alcohol; about 200 c.c. of boiling alcohol dissolve one gram. It dissolves very readily in chloroform or pyridine and crystallise from these solvents as colourless sharp needles, m.p. 236 - 237° . The pure product amounted to about 2 gms. (Found: Br = 29.2. $C_{12}H_8O_2NBr$ requires Br = 29.0 per cent.).

The *sulphate*, the *hydrochloride* and the *nitrate* were obtained as colourless needles when moderately concentrated solutions ($4 N$) of the respective acids were added to the solid substance; a clear solution was produced at first and very soon the salts began to crystallise.

The *oxalate* crystallised as long colourless fibres on adding a concentrated solution of oxalic acid to a solution of the base in dilute sulphuric acid.

The *picrate*, m. p. 255° , was deposited as stout yellow prisms when a saturated aqueous solution of picric acid was added to an acid solution of the substance.

The *dichromate* separated as four-sided prisms even from very dilute solutions.

The *ferrocyanide* formed thin plates of a pale yellow colour.

The *mercuri-chloride* separated from concentrated solutions as long, colourless needles, and the *mercuri-iodide*, which was amorphous at first, slowly changed into yellow pyramidal crystals.

The *chloroplatinate* formed pale yellow prismatic needles. (Found: Pt = 20.1 ($C_{12}H_6O_2NBr$)₂, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt = 20.3 per cent.).

1:2:3:4-Tetrahydro-quinolino-6:5- α -3-bromopyrone.

The above quinolino-bromopyrone (1 g.) was treated with (1:1 dilute) hydrochloric acid (40 c. c.) and granulated tin (4 g.) and the mixture was kept boiling gently for six hours. The clear solution was then diluted and the tin eliminated using sulphuretted hydrogen. The filtrate was then concentrated on the water-bath to small bulk and the tetrahydro compound was precipitated using dilute ammonia. It crystallises from alcohol in golden

yellow plates melting sharply at 174° ; the pure substance weighed only 0.2 g. (Found: Br = 28.65. $C_{12}H_{10}O_2NBr$ requires Br = 28.6 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* crystallises as colourless needles from moderately concentrated solutions.

The *chloroplatinate* forms yellow sharp needles. (Found: Pt = 20.0. $(C_{12}H_{10}O_2NBr)_2 \cdot H_2PtCl_6$ requires Pt = 20.1 per cent.).

The *nitroso compound* was thrown down as a flocculent precipitate when excess of dilute sodium nitrite solution was added to a solution of the tetrahydro compound in dilute hydrochloric acid. It was moderately soluble in boiling alcohol from which it crystallised as colourless rhombic plates, m. p. $195-196^{\circ}$ (decomp.).

Quinolino-6:5- α -3-bromopyronemethiodide was prepared by heating the base with methyl iodide, with the addition of a little methyl alcohol, at 140° in a sealed tube for 3 hours. It dissolved in cold water to an almost colourless solution and crystallised, on concentrating the solution, as deep yellow rectangular plates, m. p. 252° (decomp.). On boiling the aqueous solution, the methiodide slowly decomposed, giving the original quinolino-bromopyrone.

Quinolino-6:5-furan- α -carboxylic Acid.

The quinolino-bromopyrone (2 g.) was dissolved in about 50 c. c. of alcohol, a strong solution of caustic potash (5 g. in 10 c.c. of water) was added, and the mixture was boiled under reflux for four hours. On

cooling, colourless crystals of the potassium salt of the furan carboxylic acid were deposited. Water was added until a clear solution was obtained and then carefully neutralised, when the acid was slowly deposited in the crystalline condition. It was fairly soluble in boiling water and boiling alcohol and crystallised from these solvents as colourless needles which neither melted nor decomposed below 300° . The yield was satisfactory, the pure product weighing 1.5 g.

The *silver* salt was obtained as a colourless, gelatinous precipitate. (Found: Ag = 33.4. $C_{12}H_6O_3NAg$ requires Ag = 33.8 per cent.).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by saturating an alcoholic suspension of the acid with hydrogen chloride. The product was poured into water, neutralised with sodium bicarbonate and the precipitate crystallised from dilute alcohol. It was obtained as colourless felted needles m. p. 133° .

Quinolino-6:5-furan.

Quinolino-furan-carboxylic acid (2 g.) was intimately mixed with 5 times its weight of finely powdered dry sodalime and heated in a hard glass tube to dull redness for about an hour. An oil of a light brown colour having an odour somewhat resembling quinoline distilled which solidified as a hard crystalline mass. Recrystallisation from alcohol gave colourless plates m. p. 85° ; the pure product weighed 0.6 g.

The substance is readily soluble in alcohol and in most of the ordinary organic solvents (ether, chloroform, benzene), the solutions exhibiting a pale blue fluorescence. It is insoluble in cold water and dissolves appreciably in boiling water, the clear solution becoming milky on cooling. (Found: $N=8.5$. $C_{11}H_7NO$ requires $N=8.3$ per cent.).

The quinolino-furan dissolved in cold dilute acid producing light green solutions from which it was reprecipitated by the addition of ammonia. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gave a violet solution which changed to blue on warming.

The *picrate* formed light yellow prisms, m. p. 221° .

The *dichromate* was obtained as red rhombohedral crystals, m. p. 149° (decomp.).

The *mercuri-chloride* crystallised as triangular plates when fairly concentrated solutions were employed and the *mercuri-iodide* separated as colourless needles when Meyer's reagent was added to a solution of the substance in dilute acids.

The *chloroplatinate* formed yellow needles. (Found: $Pt=25.9$. $(C_{11}H_7NO)_2, H_2PtCl_6$ requires $Pt=26.1$ per cent.).

Quinolino-6:5-furan Methiodide.—The solid furan was mixed with an excess of methyl iodide and a little alcohol and heated in a sealed tube at 100° for an hour. On cooling, the solution gave a mass of yellow four-sided prisms; the product, m. p. 284° (decomp.), was pure and the yield was almost theoretical.

The methiodide dissolved easily in cold water and warm alcohol producing pale green solutions which on concentration deposit the substance in a pure, crystalline condition. It is not perceptibly decomposed by boiling water. (Found: $I=40.6$. $C_{11}H_7NO, CH_3I$ requires $I=40.6$ per cent.).

3-Bromo-6-amino-coumarin.

3-Bromo-6-nitro-coumarin (2 g.) was treated with 4*N*-acetic acid (100 c.c.), heated to about 100° on a boiling water-bath and fine iron powder (4 g.) was added in the course of an hour. The reaction product was cooled, made alkaline with sodium bicarbonate, the precipitate filtered and extracted with boiling alcohol. On cooling the amino compound crystallised as bright red needles, m. p. 192—493,° weighing 1.2 g. (Found: Br=33.5. $C_9H_6O_2NBr$ requires Br=33.3 per cent.).

2-Methyl-quinolino-6: 5- α -3-bromopyrone.

3-Bromo-6-amino-coumarin (2 g.) was treated with fuming hydrochloric and (10 c.c.) and paraldehyde (4 c.c.) added. After leaving over-night and then heating in an oil-bath for 2 hours at 130°, the resinous mass was extracted repeatedly with small quantities of boiling water till the filtrate ceased to be coloured. On rendering it alkaline with sodium carbonate, the methyl-quinolino-bromopyrone was obtained as a dark coloured flocculent precipitate; this was purified by redissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating carefully with sodium carbonate.

It is sparingly soluble in alcohol, but readily dissolved in pyridine or chloroform and crystallised from these solvents as colourless rhombohedral crystals, m. p. 243° (decomp.). The pure product weighed a little less than

a gram. (Found: Br=27.6. $C_{13}H_8O_2NBr$ requires Br=27.4 per cent.).

The salts of methylquinolino-bromopyrone closely resembled those of quinolino-bromopyrone. The *hydrochloride*, *nitrate* and *sulphate* are sparingly soluble in water and crystallised from moderately concentrated acid solutions as colourless needles, their aqueous solutions are colourless.

The *picrate*, light yellow prisms, m. p. 210° , the *dichromate*, deep yellow prismatic needles, the *mercuri-chloride* colourless silky needles, the *mercuri-iodide*, yellow flat needles and the *ferrocyanide*, glistening yellow needles, were all prepared in the usual way from and solutions of the base.

The *chloroplatinate* crystallised in sheaves of yellow needles. (Found: Pt=19.7. $(C_{13}H_8O_2NBr)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt = 19.7 per cent.).

2-Methyl-1 : 2 : 3 : 4-tetrahydro-quinolino-6 : 5-*a*-3-bromo-pyrone was obtained in the usual way by reducing methyl-quinolino-bromopyrone with tin and hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from alcohol as rhombic plates, m. p. $162-163^\circ$. (Found: Br=27.3. $C_{13}H_{12}O_2NBr$ requires Br=27.3 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride* of the base was precipitated from moderately concentrated solutions as colorless needles.

The *chloroplatinate* separated as yellow needles and the *nitroso compound* crystallised from alcohol as colourless needles, m. p. 179° .

2-Methylquinolino-6 : 5-*a*-3-bromopyronemethiodide, obtained in the usual way, crystallised from water in yellow plates, m. p. 285° (decomp.). It is insoluble in all the ordinary organic solvents and decomposed on prolonged boiling with water, regenerating the methyl-quinolino-bromopyrone.

2-Methyl-quinolino-6:5-furan-a-carboxylic Acid.—This was obtained from 2-methyl-quinolino-6:5-*a*-bromopyrone by the action of alcoholic potash. It crystallised from boiling water or alcohol in colourless flat needles which do not melt below 300°. The yield was theoretical.

The *silver* salt was precipitated as a colourless flocculent precipitate. (Found: Ag=32.1. $C_{13}H_8O_3NAg$ requires Ag=32.3 per cent.).

The *ethyl ester* when crystallised from dilute alcohol appeared as clusters of colourless needles, m. p. 107°.

2-Methyl-quinolino-6:5-furan.—This was obtained from 2-methyl-quinolino-furan-carboxylic acid by distillation with dry sodalime. It distilled as a light brown oil which when cooled in ice immediately and scratched became a crystalline solid melting at 29° approximately. On allowing the oil to stand for 24 hours, however, it solidified as a mass of colourless cubes, m. p. 84-85°: 0.6 g. of the furan was obtained by distilling 2 g. of the acid.

The methyl-quinolino-furan is readily soluble in the ordinary organic solvents, the solutions exhibiting a pale blue fluorescence. Though it is not perceptibly soluble in cold water, it dissolved to a considerable extent in boiling water. With concentrated sulphuric acid it gave a violet solution which changes to blue on warming. (Found: N=7.8. $C_{12}H_9NO$ requires N=7.7 per cent.).

The *hydrochloride*, *sulphate* and the *nitrate* are all readily soluble in water, the aqueous solutions exhibiting a faint green colour. The *picrate* crystallised as yellow prisms, m. p. 198°; the *dichromate* forms red needles, m. p. 152° (decomp.); the *ferrocyanide* is slowly deposited as light yellow plates from concentrated solutions, and the *mercuri-chloride* and the *mercuri-iodide* form clusters of colourless and light yellow needles respectively.

The *chloroptatinate* separated as tufts of yellow needles. (Found: Pt = 25.0. $(C_{12}H_9NO)_2$, H_2PtCl_6 requires Pt = 25.1 per cent.).

2-Methyl-quinolino-6:5-furan-methiodide, obtained in good yield, crystallised from dilute alcohol in bright yellow needles, m. p. 256° (decomp.). Its solutions in water and alcohol have a light green colour. (Found: I = 39.2. $C_{12}H_9NO$, CH_3I requires I = 39.1 per cent.).

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